

ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE

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Abstract: Research shows that a number of factors have a leading influence on the formation and development of tourism infrastructure. In the article, the author analyzed the factors influencing the formation and development of tourism infrastructure.

Key words: tourism, infrastructure, economy, tourism, service, tourist, tourist, currency, income, transport, hotel, geographical, economic, political, travel safety, socio-demographic.

Annotasiya: Tadqiqotlar turizm infratuzilmasini shakllanishiga va rivojlanishiga bir qator omillar yetakchi ta'sir o'tkazishini ko'rsatadi. Maqolada muallif turizm infratuzilmasini shakllanishiga va rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni tahlil etgan.

Kalit so'zlar: turizm, infratuzilma, iqtisodiyot, turizm, xizmat, sayyoh, turist, valyuta, daromad, transport, mehmonxona, geografik, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, sayohat xavfsizligi, ijtimoiy-demografik.

Аннотация: Исследования показывают, что на формирование и развитие туристической инфраструктуры ведущее влияние оказывает ряд факторов. В статье автор анализирует факторы, влияющие на формирование и развитие туристической инфраструктуры.

Ключевые слова: туризм, инфраструктура, экономика, турист, услуга, турист, валюта, доход, транспорт, гостиница, географический, экономический, политический, безопасность путешествий, социально-демографический.

Introduction. Currently, obtaining this or that information in a computer system is always open to travel agents. They can use it in a separate working mode or cooperate with counterparties using telecommunication networks of information processing tools.

At the same time, a number of factors have a leading influence on the formation and development of tourism infrastructure. Of these factors, we consider it appropriate to consider the following.

Main part. Geographical factors. People seek to get out into nature, see and enjoy a variety of scenic spots. The level and nature of the diversity of natural

conditions is of great importance for tourism and recreation. That is, the landscape, climate, diversity of flora and fauna of a particular territory are one of the main means for people to relax and restore their health.

Figure 1. Pyramid of geographical factors influencing the development of tourism infrastructure ¹.

The favorable geographical location of regions and countries plays a leading role in the development of tourism infrastructure.

For example, travel agencies advertise exotic, unique natural objects more. Especially countries such as Asia, Africa, Central and South America, Australia and Oceania attract tourists from Europe and North America with their remarkable natural exoticism. In Colombia, a unique type of tourism called “Colombian Birds” and the organization of a 24-day trip to Australia and New Zealand by the Pan American airline to find valuable stones and minerals led to the coordination and formation of the country's tourism infrastructure.

In some countries, the development of tourism infrastructure depends on the geographical location of the country and the region, namely its proximity to the sea and ocean, the nature of the coastline, the intersection of various water, road and railway routes, proximity to mountainous and forest landscapes, and the level of provision with them. In particular, the development of tourism infrastructure in Spain, Italy, France, Turkey, the Arab Republic of Egypt, Thailand, Indonesia, Singapore, and the Caribbean countries is distinguished by its geographical location. At the same time, in many cases it depends on the natural climatic conditions of countries and regions. Here, natural climatic conditions occupy a leading position. Natural climatic conditions are the main factor that makes tourism seasonal. Changes in weather, frequent occurrence of

natural disasters, and vagaries of nature lead to a sharp decrease in the flow of tourists. Therefore, the most developed regions of tourism fall on temperate climatic zones of the globe. In particular, in countries located on the coasts of the Mediterranean Sea, Black Sea, Caribbean Sea, Adriatic Sea, Baltic Sea, Sea of Japan, and South China Sea, tourism infrastructure is of international importance.

The world's oceans and sea coasts are factors that greatly influence the development of tourism infrastructure. They occupy a special place in the development of economic relations, in organizing tourism, excursions. In particular, the sea coasts of France, Spain, Italy, Turkey, Greece, Egypt, the East Coast of Romania and Bulgaria, the coasts of California and Florida in the USA, the beaches of the Bahamas and Bermuda have undoubtedly influenced the development of international tourism and resort infrastructure.

The composition of the coasts of the ocean and sea waters, which are convenient for bathing, includes the following elements: Microclimate, water temperature, depth, water waves, tides, currents, healing properties of water, cleanliness, clarity, relief of the seabed, the presence of predatory fish (sharks) and animals in the water, etc., the structure of the coastline, the quality, color, shapes of sand and sediments on the beaches, and a number of other factors affect it.

Rivers and lakes also serve as a tourism resource or wealth. They form terrestrial landscapes, create microclimate conditions, serve as fishing grounds for tourists, water sports, and provide tourist centers and resorts with clean drinking water. Currently, river and lake basins in countries such as Austria, Switzerland, Great Britain, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Finland, Canada, and the USA are considered the most developed types of tourism. However, in recent years, as a result of excessive ecological pollution of the Rhine River in Western Europe, it has been losing its former place and status in tourism and recreation, but as a result of timely measures taken by the German government, nature is now being restored here, and tourist activity is being revived again.

The role of forest resources in the development of the tourism infrastructure of countries is also significant. It plays an important role in the relaxation of tourists, balancing their emotions, creating lyrical conditions, and allowing them to live for a short time, separated from the "outside world". A number of works have been carried out in this regard in Russia, Canada, the USA, Brazil, Colombia, Venezuela, and Chile. Forests are the main source of fresh air, a

place for restoring health, and one of the main means of reducing noise in resort areas.

Another factor that attracts foreign tourists the most is the habitats of exotic (strange, wonderful) animals - reserves, state reserves, national parks, special areas allocated for hunting. There are more than a hundred centers of such fauna and flora, which are considered tourist regions and areas of Africa, Asia, Europe, Australia, America (USA, Canada).

One of the factors that attracts many foreign tourists is healing mineral waters. The main places of its occurrence are a number of countries such as Germany, Russia, Georgia, Hungary, Slovakia, the Czech Republic, Poland, Ukraine.

The types of sports in mountain conditions for foreign tourists are mountaineering (Alps, Cordillera, Himalayas, etc.), skiing (Scandinavia, Alps, Tatra Mountains), water skiing, and underwater swimming. In Germany, France, Italy, Belgium, Sweden, Great Britain, Greece and the USA, foreign tourists are widely involved in sports hunting and fishing.

Economic and geographical factors include the material and technical base of tourism, that is, the hotel fund, catering establishments (restaurant chains), sports facilities, sightseeing and sightseeing, recreation, a number of service facilities, internal and external communication networks - automobile, railway, air, sea and river transport, means of communication, the Internet. New railways, highways, sea, river, air transport, modern tourist buses, passenger cars, including comfortable car trailers with sleeping places, motorcycles, scooters, new sea and river passenger ships, motorboats, fast jet airliners, etc. All this creates great opportunities for the rapid development of tourism infrastructure.

Economic factors. Along with macroeconomic factors, microeconomic factors also have a great impact on the development of tourism. Macroeconomic instability, rising unemployment, and currency devaluation, etc., provoke and disturb society. In some cases, when people take a vacation from work, they have to stay at home and not travel anywhere. When a country's economy is booming, production.

The price of tourist products and tourist goods is one of the most important factors in people's recreation. In particular, the exchange rate plays an important role in financing tourism. The simplicity of currency exchange, its ease, etc. For example, since January 1, 2002, the introduction of the "Euro" in the countries of the European Union (in 19 countries), the transition to a single

currency for tourists in the region and a single visa system for 26 countries (based on the Schengen Agreement), and the economic and social relations between the countries of the European Union (27 countries after the UK leaves the EU from January 1, 2020).

Trade relations. Tourists traveling to foreign countries are usually interested in what they can buy there. This is unique, local handicrafts, souvenirs, purchases for relatives, family members. Such souvenirs and gifts are usually sold in supermarkets and shops in places where tourists are concentrated.

In a number of countries with developed tourism, industrial exports are developing, taking into account the demands and needs of tourists from foreign countries. Currently, countries such as the United Arab Emirates (UAE), Greece, Italy, Singapore, India, China, and South Korea have begun to sell durable goods (clothing, jewelry, household items, electronics, radios, telephones, televisions, and video equipment) to foreign tourists.

Political factors. When it comes to political factors, it also depends on the political situation in the regions and regions along important tourist routes in the countries that receive and send tourists.

It is known that the degree of stability of the internal situation in the country in many cases determines the direction of international tourism flows. Naturally, in the exchange of tourists between countries, the relations of mutual understanding between countries also play an important role. Regular diplomatic relations, agreements, contracts in the field of tourism, joint use of means of communication and transport, exchange of tourist advertisements, all this has a positive impact on the development of tourism.

Socio-demographic factors. Demographic processes in countries of the world (births, deaths, natural increase, population migration, etc.) also have an impact on the development of the international tourism sector. The increase in the population in various countries, regions and areas of the globe, especially the expansion of the circle of urban agglomerations, requires people to relax and go on tourism. In this regard, demographic factors affecting the development of tourism can be expressed as follows: common aspects of the similarity of the peoples of the world with each other, their interests; increasing active participation of people in certain professional fields in a special tourist group; increasing the proportion of women and youth in the composition of tourists; The growth of the network of resorts and sanatoriums of international importance, the increasing number of patients seeking treatment there;

changing people's views, concepts and attitudes towards the environment, etc. play a very important role.

Travel safety. With the development of tourism, ensuring the safety of tourists is becoming an increasingly important and necessary issue. Currently, for every country sending and receiving tourists in the tourism sector, measures to ensure the safety of tourists during their vacations and on transport routes should be a normal, normal part of life for each country. International disputes or military actions, international crime, terrorist incidents and events not only hinder the flow of international tourism, but also deal a huge blow to its development. In this regard, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of each country, which is the main generator (initiator) of international tourism, should inform its citizens about adverse events and incidents in the countries they travel to. Tourists should be informed about adverse events and incidents in the countries they travel to. Tourists should be informed in advance about the sanitary and hygienic condition of hotels and catering establishments in the country they are traveling to, including objective information about drinking water, and the risk of infectious diseases.

Scientific and technological progress (innovations). Scientific and technological achievements are widely used in the tourism industry and hospitality, passenger transportation, and information exchange. In air transport, tourist services are developing due to the production of new modern high-speed aircraft designed to transport large passengers.

Conclusion. Technological factors in the field of railway transport are increasingly developing, which is reflected in the increase in the speed of train travel. Currently, in countries such as Japan, China, Germany and France, the speed of high-speed passenger trains has been increased to 320-550 km per hour. The advantage of railway transport over aviation and other types of transport is that it provides the highest level of tourist safety, and railway stations are located in the city center, creating convenient opportunities for tourists. The development of telecommunications technologies and the electronics industry has made it possible to book hotel rooms and transport tickets in a computer system. The emergence of new technologies has led to qualitative changes in the organization and sale of tourist products. The future development of tourism is primarily determined by the improvement of tourist products, the development of professional travel agency networks, the scope of tour operator products, the level of use of marketing services and the connection with the human factor.

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